

FLUORIDE TOXICITY AND DEFLUORIDATION TECHNIQUES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BIOREMEDIATION

B. Prabhavathi* & Dr. D. Aruna Kumari

Lecturer in Zoology, Government College (A), Anantapur, A.P, India, 515001

**Corresponding:*

Keywords:**ABSTRACT**

Groundwater,
Fluorosis,
defluoridation,
toxicity,
bioremediation.

High concentrations of Fluoride in water leading to fluorosis, is a health disorder affecting both rural and urban populations in India. Fluoride ion in drinking water is known for both beneficial and detrimental effects on health. It is essential for the normal mineralization of bones and the formation of dental enamel with presence in small quantities [3]. However, when consumed in higher doses (>1.5mg/l), it leads to dental fluorosis or mottled enamel and excessively high concentration (>3.0mg/l) of fluoride may lead to skeletal fluorosis [6]. Contamination of water resources with fluoride beyond acceptable limits is a health-associated problem in many areas of South Asia and other regions of the world, more so in India. Fluoride from water or wastewater can be removed by an ion exchange/adsorption process or by coagulation, precipitation process. The ion exchange/adsorption can be applied to either concentrated or diluted solutions and they are capable of achieving complete removal under proper conditions. The latest technique of bioremediation is also highlighted. The method suitable for a given situation needs to be judiciously selected considering the various aspects. The paper presents the current information on fluoride in the environment and its effects on human health and available methods of defluoridation in detail.

Introduction

Water is one of the major elements essential for the sustenance of all forms of life and is available in abundance in nature covering approximately three-fourths of the surface of the earth. The chemical nature of water is one of the most important criteria that determine its usefulness for a specific need and as such not all the waters are fit for drinking; hence the problems of scarcity of drinking water. The presence of fluoride, in quantities over limits is a serious matter of concern from a public health point of view. Like any other pollutant, fluoride pollution can also occur due to both natural and manmade reasons. Fluoride toxicity is taking its toll. There is a sharp rise in the number of people with 'yellow teeth'. Cases of arthritis are on the rise. Toothless

villagers with twisted limbs are not an uncommon sight.

As a priority issue, both from the water and health angles – two perspectives that need to merge to address it completely. For decades, the emphasis on Fluorosis mitigation had been totally from the waterside, i.e., to supply Fluoride free water, with a pure source or by treatment of affected water. The push needed from the health side has been abysmally lacking, and only gaining slightly perhaps for the past decade or so. Ability and also the infrastructure for detection of Fluorosis is very poor among doctors in affected areas, so where would there be a demand for better water among patients – all that they demand is more pain-killers; making a big industry for cheap pain-killers across Fluorosis affected areas. This is why perhaps, so many defluoridation programs fail to catch up among patients. Estimates of several thousand crores worths of investments in these programs are almost down the drain. New programs are still being developed, yet, on the same path.

Fluoride in drinking water is known for both beneficial and detrimental effects on health. The fact that the problems associated with the excess fluoride in drinking water is highly endemic and widespread in countries like India prompted many researchers to explore quite a good number of both organic and inorganic materials adopting various processes from coagulation, precipitation through adsorption, Ion exchange etc. Some are good under certain conditions while others are good in other conditions. Leaching of Fluoride from the earth's crust is the chief source of fluoride content in groundwater; however, other sources like food items also add to increase the overall ingestion of fluoride into the human body. The current information on fluoride in the environment and its effects on human health, and available methods of defluoridation are presented in the following sections.

Study area:

Raptadu mandal in Anantapur district of Andhra Pradesh lies between North latitudes of 14° 30" to 14° 35" and Eastern longitudes of 77° 25" to 77° 45" (Fig. 1), and is distributed by 11 villages. It has an area of 293 sq.km. the average annual rainfall in the area is 550 mm and the temperature varies between 15°C to 42°C. It is known for its semi-arid type of climate and it's for industrially nascent and agricultural backwardness. The research region mostly reveals peninsular gneisses of Archean age made up of pink granites, schists, and composite gneisses of Dharwar age. A few newer pegmatite dykes, many dolerite dykes, and perhaps diamondiferous volcanic pipes have also been intruded upon these gneisses.

Fig. 1: Location map.

Fluoride in Environment

Fluorine (F₂) is a greenish diatomic gas. Fluorine is so highly reactive that it is never encountered in its elemental gaseous state except in some industrial processes. The fluoride occurs notably as Sellaite, fluorspar, Ca F₂; Cryolite, Na₃ Al F₆; Fluorapatite, 3Ca₃(PO₄)₂ Ca (F, Cl₂). These fluoride minerals are nearly insoluble in water. Hence fluorides will be present in groundwater only when conditions favor their solution. It is also present in seawater (0.8-1.4 ppm), in mica, and many drinking water supplies.

It is evident from the information available that a certain quantity of fluorine is essential for the formation of caries-resistant dental enamel and the normal process of mineralization in hard

tissues. The element is metabolized from both electrovalent and covalent compounds. Low fluoride concentrations stabilize the skeletal systems by increasing the size of the apatite crystals and reducing their solubility. About 95% of the fluoride in the body is deposited in hard tissues and it continues to be deposited in calcified structures even after other bone constituents (Ca, P, Mg, CO₃, and citrate) have reached a steady state. Age is an important factor in deciding to what extent fluorine is incorporated into the skeleton. The uptake almost ceases in dental enamel after the age of about 30 years.

Effect of Fluoride ingestion on human beings

Fluorosis - is a disease caused by ingestion of fluoride in excess through water, food, and air and is a serious health problem. Fluoride ingested with water goes on accumulating in bones up to the age of 55 years. At high doses, fluoride can interfere with carbohydrates, lipid-protein, vitamin, enzyme, and mineral metabolism.

Fluoride Bearing Illness

Long-term consumption of water containing 1 mg of fluoride per liter leads to dental fluorosis. White and yellow glistening patches on the teeth are seen which may eventually turn brown. The yellow and white patches when turned brown present themselves as horizontal streaks. The brown streaks may turn black and affect the whole tooth and may get pitted, perforated, and chipped off at the final stage. Dental fluorosis not only poses cosmetic problems but has serious social problems too, in terms of matrimonial problems of the children.

Skeletal fluorosis has been observed in persons when water contains more than 3-6 mg/L of fluoride. It affects young and old alike. Fluoride can also damage the fetus if the mother consumes water and food, with a high concentration of fluoride during pregnancy/breastfeeding, infant mortality due to calcification of blood vessels can also occur. It causes severe pain in the backbone and the joints and also leads to stiff joints, and increased density of bones, besides calcification of ligaments, and may also lead to paralysis.

Nonskeletal fluorosis conditions are often overlooked because of the misconception prevailing that fluoride will only affect bone and teeth. Fluoride, when consumed in excess can cause several ailments besides skeletal and dental fluorosis like Nervousness, depression tingling sensation in fingers and toes, excessive thirst, tendency to urinate frequently, muscle weakness, stiffness, pain in the muscle, and loss of muscle power and allergies like very painful skin rashes along with gastrointestinal problems and headache.

The relation between the concentration of fluoride and the biological effects is summarized [2] in the table.

Table Concentrations of fluorides and biological effects

Concentration of fluoride, ppm*	Medium	Effect
0.002	Air	Injury to vegetation
1	Water	Dental caries reduction
2 or more	Water	Mottled enamel
8	Water	10% osteosclerosis
50	Food and water	Thyroid changes
100	Food and water	Growth retardation
120	Food and water	Kidney changes
*In water-medium, ppm can be taken as equivalent to mg/L		

Fluoride removal.

Fluoride from water or wastewater can be removed by ion exchange/adsorption process or by coagulation, precipitation process. The ion exchange/adsorption can be applied to either concentrated or diluted solutions and they are capable of achieving complete removal under proper conditions. Of late, bioremediation methods are also gaining prominence in fluoride removal.

The method involving the addition in sequence, of an alkali, chlorine, and aluminium sulphate or aluminium chloride or both was developed [1] It is cheap and is used extensively in India. Though lime softening accomplishes fluoride removal, its high initial cost, large dosage, and alkaline pH of the treated water render it unsuitable for field application. The large dosage and alkaline pH of the treated water render it unsuitable for field application.

Activated alumina is a granular, highly porous material consisting essentially of aluminum trihydrate. It is widely used as a commercial desiccant and in many gas drying processes. The ability of activated alumina to remove fluoride depends on other aspects of the chemistry of water as well. Such factors as hardness, silica, boron, etc., if present in the water will interfere with fluoride removal and reduce the efficiency of the system. The use of activated alumina in a continuous flow fluidized system is an economical and efficient method for defluoridating water supplies [4]. The process could reduce the fluoride levels to 0.1 mg/L. The operational, control,

and maintenance problems, mainly clogging of the bed, maybe averted with this method.

The uptake of fluoride onto the surface of bone was one of the early methods suggested for defluoridation of water supplies [5]. The process was reportedly one of the ion exchanges in which the carbonate radical of the apatite comprising bone, $\text{Ca}(\text{PO}_4)_6 \cdot \text{CaCO}_3$ was replaced by fluoride to form insoluble fluorapatite. Bone char produced by carbonizing bone at a temperature of 1100-1600°C had superior qualities to those of unprocessed bone and hence replaced bone as defluoridating agent.

Most of the carbons prepared from different carbonaceous sources showed fluoride removal capacity after alum impregnation. High Fluoride removal capacities of various types of activated carbons had been reported [7]. Alkali-digested alum-impregnated paddy husk carbon was an efficient defluoridating agent [8]. Alkali digested (1% KOH) & alum soaked (2% alum) carbon removed 320 mg fluoride per kg & showed maximum removal efficiency at pH 7.0 [9].

Investigations have shown that carbonized sawdust when quenched in 2% alum solution forms an excellent defluoridating carbon [10]. The defluoridating process is stoichiometric and equilibrium is established between carbon & fluoride. On exhaustion (after continued use) the carbon can be regenerated by passing 0.2 to 0.5% alum solutions. Activated carbon prepared by other workers from cotton waste, coffee waste, coconut waste, etc., was tried for defluoridation but all these materials proved to be of academic interest only [1].

The fluorides in waters containing Magnesium, when treated with lime, are adsorbed on Magnesium hydroxide flocs enabling fluoride removal [11, 12]. In this case, the water must be treated to caustic alkalinity of 30 mg fluoride/L, a pH of 10.5 or above, and as such recarbonation is necessary [13]. Magnesia and calcined magnesite have also been used for fluoride removal from water and fluoride removal capacity was reported to be better at high temperature [14].

Strong base exchange resins remove fluorides either on the hydroxyl cycle or chloride cycle along with anions [15, 16]. Since the proportional quantity of fluoride as compared to other anions is very small, the effective capacity of such resins works out quite low. Some inorganic ion exchangers, eg. complex metal chloride silicates, formed from barium or ferric chloride with silicic acid, also exchanged fluoride for chloride.

Cation exchange resins impregnable with alum solution have been found to act as defluoridating agents. Alum-treated cation exchange resins were used for defluorination [17]. [18] [19]. 'Avaram Bark' based cation exchange resins, had been reported to work effectively in removing fluoride from water [20].

Investigations were conducted to study the usefulness of magnesia in fluoride removal. The studies established that magnesia removed the excess fluorides, but large doses were

necessary. Moreover, the pH of the treated water was beyond 10 and its correction by acidification or recarbonation was necessary. All this adds to the cost and complexity of operations.

Bioremediation techniques

To overcome the limitations of conventional defluoridation techniques, the utilization of microorganisms is the latest practice to control the fluoride content in water. Microorganisms can establish biosorption resistance to various contaminants [21], as the bacterial cell wall contains binding groups of toxic pollutants like sulfhydryl, phosphates, carboxylates and amines that aid in metal ion interaction [22]. Microorganisms are playing a key role in the biosorption of polluted water contaminants over the last few decades [23,24]. *Azolla filiculoides* [25], *Providencia vermicola*, cyanobacteria, and *Aspergillus niger* are few microorganisms reported to successfully remove fluoride from aqueous solution. The advantages of using microorganisms over other treatments are, ease of operation and lower sludge production. Many studies have confirmed that microorganisms have a high affinity to metals and non-metals through various pathways. Some bacterial organisms secrete anion-binding compounds of high affinity, called ionophores [28]. Hence, the reduction of fluoride concentration from the aqueous solutions is a more sought-after defluorination technique.

Fluoride is composed of a proton (HF). Hydrogen fluoride can easily traverse the cell membrane and act as a proton conductor. Through this, micro-organisms with adaptation mechanisms remove fluoride from the environment which makes it less accessible in the field.

Conclusions

Groundwater serves as the primary source of drinking water in most of Asian countries, including India. Due to increasing population, urbanization, industrialization, and agricultural development, our country's demand for drinking and irrigation groundwater is increasing continuously. On the other hand, due to industrialization and the developmental process, water quality is also deteriorating as water aquifers are under stress conditions. In terms of groundwater and soil toxicity, fluoride is the most important ion contaminant due to its high potency and causes serious health hazards such as fluorosis. The need of the hour is to improve prevention and recovery strategies to mitigate the effects of this pollution. Already numerous modern methods of defluoridation such as coagulation precipitation, electro-dialysis, nano-filtration, etc. are available. However, these traditional approaches have certain drawbacks including higher cost, heavy energy consumption, secondary contaminants, and lower efficiency.

In this regard, bioremediation could be a cost-saving and environmentally friendly approach to removing fluoride compounds from groundwater. Microbes with degradation or adsorption potential can be used to bioremediate fluoride contaminated water. This technique can be applied in treating fluoride-contaminated waters to save millions of lives from fluorosis and the technique can also overcome some of the limitations of the conventional techniques.

References:

1. Annadurai, S. T., Arivalagan, P., Sundaram, R., Mariappan, R., & Munusamy, A. P. (2019). Batch and column approach on biosorption of fluoride from aqueous medium using live, dead and various pretreated *Aspergillus niger* (FS18) biomass. *Surfaces and Interfaces*, 15, 60-69.
2. Ayoob, S., Gupta, A. K., & Bhat, V. T. (2008). A conceptual overview on sustainable technologies for the defluoridation of drinking water. *Critical reviews in environmental science and technology*, 38(6), 401-470.
3. Babovich, R. D. (1957). Rendering water fluorine free at the source of supply. In *Chemical Abstracts* (Vol. 51, p. 1840).
4. Bulusu, K. R., BB, S., & WG, N. (1979). Fluorides in water, defluoridation methods and their limitations.
5. Chouhan, S., Tuteja, U., & Flora, S. J. S. (2012). Isolation, identification and characterization of fluoride resistant bacteria: possible role in bioremediation. *Applied biochemistry and microbiology*, 48(1), 43-50.
6. Doble, M., & Kumar, A. (2005). *Biotreatment of industrial effluents*. Elsevier.
7. Dean, H. T., & Elvolve, E. (1938). Facts about fluorides. In *Chemical Abstracts* (Vol. 32, p. 5119).
8. Golla, V. S., & Badapalli, P. K. (2021). Evaluation of water quality for drinking and irrigation purposes and Fluoride Health Hazard Risk Assessment (HHRA) in parts of semi-arid regions in the south-eastern part of India. *International Journal of Energy and Water Resources*, 1-9.
9. Golla, V., Badapalli, P. K., & Mannala, P. (2021). Assessment of groundwater quality for drinking and irrigation in semi-arid regions of Andhra Pradesh, Southern India, using multivariate statistical analysis. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 14(19), 1-11.

10. Igiri, B. E., Okoduwa, S. I., Idoko, G. O., Akabuogu, E. P., Adeyi, A. O., & Ejiogu, I. K. (2018). Toxicity and bioremediation of heavy metals contaminated ecosystem from tannery wastewater: a review. *Journal of toxicology*, 2018.
11. Jolly, S. S., Sing, B. M., & Mathur, O. C. (1969). Endemic fluorosis in Punjab (India). *The American journal of medicine*, 47(4), 553-563.
12. Kleinübing, S. J., Da Silva, E. A., Da Silva, M. G. C., & Guibal, E. (2011). Equilibrium of Cu (II) and Ni (II) biosorption by marine alga *Sargassum filipendula* in a dynamic system: competitiveness and selectivity. *Bioresource Technology*, 102(7), 4610-4617.
13. Kunin, R., & Mc Garvey, F. (1948). Fluoride Removal by Strong Base Anion Exchange Resins. *Industrial Engineering Chemistry*, 41, 1265.
14. Mondal, N. K., Samanta, A., Dutta, S., & Chattoraj, S. (2017). Optimization of Cr (VI) biosorption onto *Aspergillus niger* using 3-level Box-Behnken design: equilibrium, kinetic, thermodynamic and regeneration studies. *Journal of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology*, 15(1), 151-160.
15. Moudarzi, F., & Sheljani, K. (2016). Fluoride and environment. *World News of Natural Sciences*, 3.
16. Mukherjee, S., Sahu, P., & Halder, G. (2017). Microbial remediation of fluoride-contaminated water via a novel bacterium *Providencia vermicola* (KX926492). *Journal of environmental management*, 204, 413-423.
17. Nagendra Rao, C. (2003, December). Fluoride and environment-a review. In *Proceedings of the third international conference on environment and health*, Chennai, India (pp. 15-17).
18. Nagaraju, A., Thejaswi, A., & Aitkenhead-Peterson, J. A. (2017). Fluoride and heavy metal accumulation by vegetation in the fluoride affected area of Talupula, Anantapur district, Andhra Pradesh. *Journal of the Geological Society of India*, 89(1), 27-32.
19. Rao, S. L. (2004). Fluoride Toxicity in Raptadu Mandal, Anantapur District. *Environmental Contamination and Bioreclamation*, 194.
20. Reddy, A. G. S., Niranjan Kumar, K., Subba Rao, D., & Sambashiva Rao, S. (2009). Assessment of nitrate contamination due to groundwater pollution in north eastern part of Anantapur District, AP India. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 148(1), 463-476.
21. Runaska, W., Kawane, M., & Kajima, T. (1951). Removal of fluoride ion by anion exchange resin. In *Chemical Abstracts* (Vol. 45, p. 5033).
22. Robertson, R. (1939). Report of the Water Pollution Reserch Board for the Year Ending June, 30 1938. In *Chemical Abstracts* (Vol. 33, p. 8340).

23. Shanker, A. S., Srinivasulu, D., & Pindi, P. K. (2020). A study on bioremediation of fluoride-contaminated water via a novel bacterium *Acinetobacter* sp.(GU566361) isolated from potable water. *Results in Chemistry*, 2, 100070.
24. Swope, H. G., & Hess, R. H. (1937). Removal of fluorides from natural waters by defluorite. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry*, 29(4), 424-427.
25. Zazouli, M. A., Mahvi, A. H., Dobaradaran, S., Barafrashtehpour, M., Mahdavi, Y., & Balarak, D. (2014). Adsorption of fluoride from aqueous solution by modified *Azolla filiculoides*. *Adsorption*, 47(4), 349-35